

1 **Catalytic site targeting in HER2+ breast cancer for the treatment of CNS metastasis: PPP4C.**

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6 Up to 50% of patients with HER2+ subtype breast cancer develop metastasis to the central nervous
7 system, most commonly the brain, demanding rapid therapeutic approaches to limit spread of the HER2+
8 primary tumor to distant sites (1-3). We recently described the existence of a group of genes that reside
9 proximal to *ERBB2* (the gene that encodes the human epidermal growth factor *HER2*) at 17q12: their
10 differential expression in HER2+ breast cancer, their up-regulation in HER2+ breast cancer, their
11 differential expression and up-regulation in central nervous system (CNS) metastasis and, based on
12 human survival studies, their function in supporting metastasis to the CNS, indicating that the predilection
13 of HER2+ patients to develop CNS metastasis was a phenomena attributable to the disease and not
14 HER2+-targeted therapies (4). Disease recurrence following disease remission (relapse), resistance to
15 trastuzumab or otherwise inadequate long-term control of disease are challenges that limit effectiveness of
16 existing HER2+-targeted therapies. We utilized whole transcriptome technologies (5, 6) to measure total
17 transcription in the brain metastases of humans with HER2+ breast cancer. We describe here one
18 member of a group of molecules with available catalytic sites for small molecule inhibition that is
19 up-regulated and differentially expressed in CNS metastatic HER2+ breast cancer, PPP4C, as a candidate
20 therapeutic target for the medical management of CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer.
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CRISPR-based reverse genetic screening of human HER2+ organoids or primary tumor cells freshly isolated from patients with HER2+ breast cancer with limited exposure to artificial culture conditions have not yet been described (7, 8). These genetic technologies, though not yet implemented, when done so will likely facilitate discovery of therapeutic vulnerabilities in HER2+ disease with rapidity and ease. Management of major public health problems requires research (bench)-based management in the short run and long run (9). One example of such a major problem is CNS metastasis in HER2+ breast cancer (10-13): this is a type of cancer that affects a human sex with relatively high frequency, a subtype of that cancer that is diagnosed in approximately one quarter of patients diagnosed with that cancer, and a specific complication of the subtype that develops in half of affected patients.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with breast cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms, "regional" metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Our hypothesis and working strategy dictates that in the short-run, disease complications and therapeutic limitations are best managed through identification of therapeutic targets by whole transcriptome differential expression analyses (subtraction analysis) in conjunction with the use of more recently developed broad-spectrum and targeted chemotherapeutics like inhibitors of CDK4/6 and PARP1/2 (14), respectively and in the long-run, will be enhanced and fully complemented by reverse genetic screening strategies to blindly identify disease-specific, subtype-specific and metastasis-specific therapeutic vulnerabilities augmented by novel immunotherapy approaches. Here we describe one such target identified through rigorous study of the HER2+ CNS metastasis transcriptome: a therapeutic target with an available catalytic site that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific: PPP4C.

Results

Figure 1: PPP4C is differentially expressed in HER2+ breast cancer.

I. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=8 primary tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer

n=5 brain metastases (tumor) from humans with HER2+ breast cancer (breast; human; HER2+)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
5531	9.09E-04	0.2719	-3.317309	-0.90204304	4508.24	PPP4C	2453/21403	88.5

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the normal breast tissue and in primary tumors of humans with HER2+ breast cancer (5), we discovered differential expression of protein phosphatase 4 catalytic subunit, encoded by *PPP4C* in CNS metastatic HER2+ breast cancer in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of PPP4C changed more than nearly 90% of the human CNS metastatic transcriptome in HER2+ breast cancer when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,403 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP4C messenger RNA in HER2+ brain metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PPP4C during disease progression in the HER2+ breast cancer subtype.

II. Primary tumors of the breast from humans with breast cancer: HER2+ subtype

n=11 tumors from humans with HER2+ breast cancer

n=3 brain metastases (tumor) from humans with HER2+ breast cancer (breast; human; HER2+)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
5944	1.42E-01	-1.55	-4.995	-5.42E-01	PPP4C	5182/17,581	70.5

1 Through measurement total transcription in the brain metastases of humans with breast cancer as
2 compared to primary tumors of the breast, in a second microarray dataset (6) from independent
3 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of PPP4C in breast cancer
4 CNS metastasis in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of PPP4C here changed more than 70% of the
5 CNS metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this
6 case, 17,581 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of PPP4C
7 messenger RNA in brain metastases, demonstrating up-regulation of PPP4C during disease progression
8 and metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

9 Thus, differential and increased expression of PPP4C defines the CNS metastatic transcriptome in
10 human breast cancer.

11 **Discussion**

12 Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during
13 treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvantive chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like
14 trastuzumab). Small molecule inhibitors of PPP4C, once evaluated for toxicity and safety, can immediately
15 be tested for efficacy in patients with HER2+ metastasis, with the goal of identifying the most effective
16 small molecules for chemotherapeutic management of HER2+ disease in humans. We recently used
17 primary tumor transcriptome data to identify multiple phosphatases that we deemed candidate therapeutic
18 targets in management of breast cancer, and fortuitously found their decreased expression was
19 specifically linked to superior overall survival in patients with HER2+ breast cancer (15, 16). A
20 multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis,
21 replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase is most likely to be most effective
22 in limiting tumor clone resistance (17).
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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the CNS and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE10893 for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published) and R-based computational methods.